

NEODC Data Archive

NEODC datasets are available for free download to registered users:

● **Airborne:**

Remote sensing data & aerial photography from the NERC ARSF
NEXTMap Britain digital elevation data

● **Satellite:**

LANDSAT, Envisat MERIS, SCIAMACHY, MIPAS
MetOp IASI, GOME-2, AVHRR-3

Derived EO datasets: MERIS MTCI, AVHRR FASIR

(A)ATSR data – 17 years of global Sea Surface Temperature

● **Campaigns:**

SHAC 2000 SAR and Hyperspectral Airborne Campaign

NCAVEO 2006 field experiment

ARSF aerial photograph, NERC

ARSF ATM, NERC

AATSR, STFC/Defra/ESA/NERC

MERIS MTCI, ESA/Infoterra

AATSR Global SST, STFC/Defra/ESA/NERC

NEODC Services

- Data management support for the National Centre for Earth Observation and the wider community of EO data users
- Register, search the catalogue and request access to data on www.neodc.rl.ac.uk
- Web services for on-line data manipulation
- We welcome email enquiries : neodc@rl.ac.uk